

An extension of the Sea Surface Levelling method for determining the alignment accuracy of offshore scanning lidars

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Motivation

- Scanning Lidars enable wind measurements over several kilometers with flexible scan patterns
- Small misalignments result in significant deviations in measurement points
- Calibrated systems reduce wind measurement uncertainty

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- Scanning Lidars enable wind measurements over several kilometers with flexible scan patterns
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- Calibrated systems reduce wind measurement uncertainty
- Limited availability of hard targets for calibration in offshore environments
- Sea Surface Levelling (**SSL**) as a practical calibration approach (¹Rott et al. 2022, ²Gramitzky et al. 2024)

Research Questions

- How can the SSL approach be generalized beyond previous methods?
 - Can it be independent of scan pattern?
 - Can it include elevation offset?
 - Can it include the Earth curvature
- How accurate is SSL and which factors influence uncertainty?
 - How large is the ranging error?
 - How strong is the wave influence?

Parameters influencing Lidar beam orientation

- Elevation, Azimuth: defining beam direction
- Pitch, Roll: angular rotations responsible for tilting
- Elevation Offset: vertical displacement independent of azimuth angle

Sea Surface Levelling (SSL) Method

Extension of the Sea Surface Levelling Method

- Measurement of distance to sea surface (r) for different elevation and azimuth angles
- Elevation scan sector $[\varphi_{start}, \varphi_{end}]$
- Azimuth scan sector $[0^\circ, 360^\circ]$

Determination of distance based on CNR signal

- Description of the CNR (Carrier-to-Noise-Ratio) signal via sigmoid and linear function

$$CNR(d) = \frac{(CNR_{high} - CNR_{low}) \cdot (1 + A \cdot (d - i_p))}{1 + \exp((d - i_p) \cdot g)} + CNR_{low}$$

- Determination of the inflection point i_p for the distance by fitting the function using CNR data

SSL measurement data

Data basis

Elevation vs. Distance to Sea Surface

Correction with applied tilt & elevation offset

- Scanning Lidar 400S (Vaisala), offshore campaign
- Repeated SSL scans over 9 hours (wind < 4 m/s)
- 2 different Range Height Indicator Scans (RHI 1, RHI 2)

- Example: RHI 1 [-1.5, -0.3] for one time step

- Red line: modeled elevation angle
- Robust fit: RMSE of 0.03°

Modelled influence of a distance error on elevation offset

- Model deviations on elevation offset based on distance to sea surface data with additional distance error
- Assumption of incorrect estimation of distance to sea surface by half probe volume length (-37.5m)
- Start and end points of the elevation range are shown in x- and y-axis
- Resulting elevation offset deviations for different RHI settings:
 - RHI 1 [-1.5, -0.3]: approx. 0.03°
 - RHI 2 [-3.0, -1.5]: approx. 0.16°

Measured elevation offset of the repeated SSL over time

- Investigation of 2 different RHI settings
 - RHI 1 from -1.5° to -0.3° (green)
 - RHI 2 from -3° to -1.5° (orange)
- Blue line represents the elevation offset determined from the hard target test
- Derived elevation offsets are strongly influenced by the RHI settings

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- Blue line represents the elevation offset determined from the hard target test
- Derived elevation offsets are strongly influenced by the RHI settings
- Distance correction of half the pulse length (-37.5m)
- Differences between RHI 1 and RHI 2 settings are much smaller

Modelled influence of waves on the elevation offset

- Wave model with sinusoidal shape in x-direction
- Amplitude with significant wave height (Rayleigh distributed)
- Intersection calculation between laser beam and wave surface resulting in varying distance determinations
- Modelled distances as input for extended SSL equation
- Deviations in elevation offset resulting from wave influence

Influence of waves on the elevation offset

- Wave characteristics aligned with measurement campaign:
 - Significant wave height: 1 m
 - Wavelength: 25 m
- Wave-induced elevation offset error significant at steep elevation angles and short intervals
- Resulting elevation offset deviations:
 - RHI 1: $< 0.03^\circ$
 - RHI 2: $< 0.02^\circ$

Results of the repeated SSL over time – pitch and roll

- Period without platform movements (blue: wind turbine inclinometer)
- Deviations over time in pitch, roll under 0.02°
- Distance correction has hardly any influence

Conclusion

- How can the SSL approach be generalized beyond previous methods?
 - Independent of scan pattern the extended SSL method allow determination of elevation offset in addition to pitch and roll
- How accurate is SSL and which factors influence uncertainty?
 - Pitch and roll remain robust across various settings
 - Elevation offset is sensitive to distance errors, especially at steeper angles
 - Sigmoid inflection point may not accurately reflect the true dipping point
 - Wave influence affects only measurements with small elevation intervals
 - SSL robust method to determine pitch, roll and elevation offset

For RHI 1:

Distance error Φ	0.02°
Wave error Φ	0.03°
RMSE	0.03°

Preprint available:

<https://wes.copernicus.org/preprints/wes-2025-191/>

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